

Onboard AI for Enhanced FDIR: Revolutionizing Spacecraft Operations with Anomaly Detection

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Spacecraft operate in harsh environments with relevant computational constraints as well as limited communication to Earth. Traditional Fault Detection, Isolation, and Recovery (FDIR) systems rely on pre-programmed thresholds, which can miss unforeseen anomalies, thus requiring frequent human intervention from ground. This paper explores the potential of onboard Artificial Intelligence (AI) for enhanced FDIR. By continuously analyzing spacecraft telemetry data, onboard AI can detect anomalies in real-time, enabling faster and more precise responses. This approach promises to revolutionize spacecraft operations by improving autonomy, reducing reliance on ground intervention, and ensuring mission success. The paper discusses how Machine Learning based methods can enhance spacecraft Fault Detection capabilities. In particular, the performance of methods such as Principal Component Analysis, Autoregressive model, Autoencoder, and Long Short-Term Memory networks are explored. The considered use-case is based on telemetry data from Reaction Wheels, thus the AOC subsystem. This work also addresses challenges associated with implementing onboard AI, such as computational resource constraints and radiation hardening. Finally, a performance comparison between the selected methods in different conditions closes the discussion.

1 Introduction

Space missions heavily relies on the effective implementation of Spacecraft Prognostic and Health Management systems, also known as Fault Detection, Isolation, and Recovery (FDIR). These essential systems greatly influence spacecraft reliability, availability, and safety. To accommodate the complexity and operational demands of modern space systems, efficient health monitoring and fault detection systems are crucial. However, current methods often require expert knowledge for development and maintenance, making cost-effective ground operations challenging. Traditional approaches utilize deterministic monitoring techniques, such as the "Out-Of-Limits" (OOL) method, which involves pre-established threshold values for telemetry sensors. Coupled with their limitations, the increasing workload due to the increasing number of satellites in orbit high-

lights the need for innovative solutions.

Advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) offer promising opportunities for improving spacecraft health monitoring processes. ML techniques, such as One-Class Support Vector Machines (OCSVMs) and Neural Networks based on Autoencoders [1, 2] (AEs), allow for the modeling and detection of anomalies in telemetry data by learning normal system behavior and identifying deviations. As spacecraft telemetry data becomes increasingly valuable, a data-driven approach can automate complex tasks like failure detection and prognostics, for instance in Attitude and Orbit Control (AOC) subsystem, reducing the workload on ground operations engineers.

In recent years, several researchers have studied how to exploit ML methods to improve anomaly detection capabilities in space systems [3–10]. In this work, we discuss the use of ML models to enhance the Fault Identification for more efficient and accurate anomaly detection in new generation FDIR systems. We investigate the effectiveness of several anomaly detectors monitoring the reaction wheels in an AOC subsystem and we validate them with synthetic anomalies designed to emulate possible real-world anomalies. We also discuss the implementation aspects as real-time inference on resource-constrained hardware can be challenging on space-qualified processors.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the selection of ML models, the use cases, and the anomalies considered in this study. Section 3 discussed the implementation challenges in a space environment. Section 4 show the performance of the selected models. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2 ML Models for Anomaly Detection

Detection of behavior that deviates from nominal observations is currently approached through OOL algorithms that compare telemetry data with predefined thresholds. To make the detector more effective, we explore the detection capability of a short list of promising methods. All the in-

Figure 1: Block scheme of the implemented ML/AI-based anomaly detector for enhanced FDIR.

investigated methods model normal statistics by observing long stretches of normal behavior. An alert is raised when a mismatch between the incoming piece of data and the learned model is detected. To quantify this mismatch, all investigated methods generate anomaly scores and compare them with properly designed thresholds to produce the final binary outcomes, i.e., the final label. The entire processing chain is depicted in Fig. 1.

Such a general scheme can be implemented in different ways, depending on the technique adopted to identify the normal behavior. We propose here three main categories:

- **Matching with Compression (MC):** A lossy compression mechanism must learn the characteristics of the nominal data to minimize the information loss. As a consequence, when an anomaly – data that deviates from the typical behavior – occurs, the loss of information is higher and it reflects in a higher reconstruction error. As a result, such an error can be used as an anomaly score. We consider two different methods: *i*) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [11]; *ii*) AEs, which consist of a family of Neural Network working as a non-linear generalization of PCA.
- **Matching with Prediction (MP):** similarly to MC, a predictor must learn the characteristics of the nominal data to minimize the prediction error and a greater error is likely to correspond to anomalous instances. As a result, the prediction error can be used as an anomaly score. We consider two possible predictors: *i*) an Autoregressive (AR) model [12]; *ii*) a recurrent network based on three stacked layers equipped with long short-term memory cells (LSTM) [13].
- **Reference Models for anomaly detection (RM):** this last family of detectors groups some established anomaly detection methods from ML. Two examples included here are Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [14] and OCSVMs [15]. These methods directly compute an anomaly score based on how much a data point deviates from the expected behavior.

Fig. 2 visualizes how each family of methods implements the processing chain. MC uses an encoder-decoder architecture to compress and decompress data, with the reconstruction error acting as the anomaly score. MP and RM involve

Figure 2: Processing chain of chunks of telemetry data for MC, MP, and RM anomaly detectors.

a single block for prediction or direct anomaly score computation, respectively.

2.1 Use cases

We refer to a real operational spacecraft use case to verify and quantify the capabilities of all considered detectors. Specifically, we employ data extracted from the monitoring system of an on-board attitude control system equipped with Reaction Wheels (RWs). These are used to provide continuous fine attitude control of the orbit, both during nominal operations and in the event of a required response to an environmental disturbance. A RW is generally driven by an electric motor, which is monitored by sensors whose readings are the input to the ML/AI-based detectors. The dataset used in this work refers to three different configurations, reflecting three possible levels of monitoring: *i*) single channel, the detector only observes data from a given time series of a designed RW; *ii*) sub-system, the detector processes portions of all time series available for a single RW; *iii*) entire system, the detector computes a single score for the whole navigation system which includes four RWs.

2.2 Validation based on synthetic anomalies

The dataset is organized as chunks $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times l}$ of non-overlapping windows of n sensor readings from l time-series. Hence, $l = 1$ in the single channel scenario, $l = 4$ in the sub-system configuration, while the entire system setting requires $l = 16$. Chunks representing the nominal behavior are used to determine the model parameters in training/validation. To assess the detection capabilities, we refer to the synthetic injection of 5 different sources of abnormalities reported below.

- **Additive noise:** instances of zero-mean white Gaussian noise are added to each entry of each data instance x . The standard deviation σ controls the noise intensity.

- **Offset:** a constant value is added to each entry of each data instance x . The sign is randomly assigned while the magnitude controls the noise intensity.
- **Glitch:** here l spikes with a random sign are added to each column of x in correspondence of a random sample among the n ones contained in a window. The magnitude of each spike controls the noise intensity.
- **Rotation:** a corrupted instance is generated by rotating each column of x along a random direction. The value of the angle controls the level of abnormalities.
- **Saturation:** the magnitude of the largest samples in a window is clipped to a certain saturation value. The lower the saturation value, the larger the noise intensity.

In each of these anomalies, the tuning of the main parameter controlling the level of abnormality is such that the corresponding signal-to-noise ratio is 0dB.

3 Radiation-hardened Processor implementation

The choice of a processor for ML applications in space is subjected to a large number of restrictions due to the harsh space environment. The exposure to high levels of radiation, extreme temperatures, and the vacuum of space significantly impact the performance and longevity of these processors. High-energy particles strike and penetrate the semiconductor material causing a variety of damaging effects, ranging from temporary malfunctions to permanent damage or even total destruction of the component. Nowadays, chip manufacturers offer commercial products combining remarkable radiation-tolerance characteristics with high-performance computation capabilities. However, in many scenarios, it becomes necessary to use radiation-hardened (rad-hard) components that have been specifically designed and tested to withstand high levels of radiation. The specific techniques used for these components result in a significant reduction of performances. The higher production costs and the consolidated trend in the space industry to prefer well tested and certified solutions, further delay the adoption of more powerful solution. The amount of available memory is a scarce resource as well and the cost of rad-hard memories is very high. Moreover, the low bandwidth available for satellite transmissions limits the capability to update applications, when necessary. Due to these factors, the state of the art for platforms currently used in space missions is based on a (up to) quad-core processor with few megabytes available for space applications. To cope with these constraints, the ML algorithms have been deployed into a self-contained standard C language library. Due to this, the library is highly portable and can run on virtually any platform that supports a C compiler. The library has a very reduced footprint on non-volatile memory, less than 1

Megabytes, and it is able to scale very well with the number of parameters. RAM memory occupancy is instead affected by input data size and model configuration.

4 Results

In this section, we focus on fine-tuning the anomaly detectors. We assess their effectiveness across the three configurations outlined in Section 2.1 by involving the synthetic anomalies described in Section 2.2. Our goal is to strike a balance between high detection rates and the computational constraints of space-qualified processors.

4.1 Tuning of ML/AI methods

We assess the six detectors in detecting the five anomaly types to select the hyper-parameter combination that guarantees the best performance. The performance of the detectors is evaluated in terms of probability of detection P_{det} [2] defined as

$$P_{det} = \begin{cases} AUC & \text{if } AUC \geq 0.5 \\ 1 - AUC & \text{if } AUC < 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with AUC indicating the Area-Under-the ROC Curve [16]. In contrast to accuracy, AUC is computed from the anomaly scores independently of any threshold.

Among the hyper-parameter characterizing all methods, window size n is crucial as it significantly impacts computational cost. A larger n implies a higher number of data points to be processed for a single anomaly score and often leads to a higher number of parameters in the ML/AI model. In Table 1, we report the best hyper-parameter configuration identified for each detection method. Note that each setting is compliant with the limitations discussed in Section 3.

In the MC family, PCA is characterized by the dimension of the latent space, while AE is mainly defined by the number of 1-dimensional convolutional layers. As for the MP detectors, the AR model is characterized by the filter order, while, for the neural counterpart, we indicate the number of LSTM blocks. Finally, in the RM category, LOF is characterized by the number of considered nearest neighbors and OCSVM by the contamination fraction. In all cases, as we move from $l = 1$ to $l = 16$, the window size decreases to accommodate multiple telemetries being monitored simultaneously.

4.2 Detection capabilities

We refer to Figure 3 to examine the results in terms of P_{det} and to assess the robustness and sensitivity of the designed methods, configured as in Table 1, for each use case of interest. Each radar chart compares the detection capabilities in the three scenarios indicated in the legend. The axes indicate the effectiveness of detection of the respective anomaly type, with 1 indicating the best performance. The columns

Figure 3: Performance comparison in terms of P_{det} under three scenarios: entire system (green), sub-system (blue), and single channel (red). In the columns from left to right: methods belonging to the categories MC, MP, and RM, respectively.

Table 1: Configuration of the main parameters characterizing the selected ML/AI-based methods.

	Method	single channel setting, $l = 1$	sub-system setting, $l = 4$	entire system setting, $l = 16$
MC	PCA	$n = 100$, latent space dim = 70	$n = 50$, latent space dim = 150	$n = 25$, latent space dim = 300
	AE	$n = 40$, 6 conv. layer	$n = 40$, 6 conv. layer	$n = 40$, 6 conv. layer
MP	AR	$n = 100$, filter order = 3	$n = 50$, filter order = 4	$n = 25$, filter order = 4
	LSTM	$n = 30$, 3 LSTM stacked layers	$n = 30$, 3 LSTM stacked layers	$n = 30$, 3 LSTM stacked layers
RM	LOF	$n = 100$, examples/neigh. = 200	$n = 50$, examples/neigh. = 50	$n = 25$, examples/neigh. = 50
	OCSVM	$n = 100$, contam. = 0.01	$n = 50$, contam. = 0.001	$n = 25$, contam. = 0.001

show two methods from each family of detectors: PCA and AE in the left column, AR and LSTM in the middle column, and LOF and OCSVM in the right column. We observed that the injection of additive noise and glitches is detected effectively in all scenarios. For the remaining anomalies, the detection performance varies depending on the system configuration. Considering the entire system and the sub-system cases, the performance on the offset anomaly is excellent for all methods except AR. However, detecting the presence of this irregularity in the single channel configuration is challenging for all methods. The rotation anomaly is effectively detected by all methods when the entire system and subsystem telemetries are monitored, with OCSVM exhibiting slightly lower performance. PCA, AR, and LOF also succeed in the single channel case, while the remaining methods - especially AE - perform quite poorly. Finally, the most variable performance is observed on the saturation anomaly, with PCA achieving the overall best results and OCSVM excelling only in the single channel case.

5 Discussion

This work investigated the effectiveness of different ML/AI-based anomaly detection techniques to enhance the functionalities of on-board FDIR systems in spacecrafts. We explored the trade-off between achieving high detection rates and accommodating the computational constraints of space-qualified processors. This work demonstrates the potential of using ML-based anomaly detection to enhance the capabilities of on-board FDIR systems, leading to more autonomous and reliable spacecraft operations.

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